

THE WAYS OF OVERCOMING SPEAKING BARRIERS IN STUDENTS

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Abstract:

In this research we will try to find causes of speaking barriers among the students such as anxiety, afraid of public attention and solve problems by using different kind of methods.

Key words: anxiety, lack of confidence, afraid of doing mistakes

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English, there are for mean skills that we know namely listening skills writing skills reading skills and speaking skill but this research will be focused on the speaking ability, or speaking skill. Speaking is an important part of effective communication speaking is a tool of communication and use it to share any information speaking is one of the most important and essential skills that must be practiced to communicate orally [4].

Harmer stated that speaking is the core skill of mastering how to speak fluently. Speaking is cap potential to manner facts and language [2]. Moreover, Quaintly defines «speaking is a process of transmitting thoughts and facts based on the situations [5].

Speaking Difficulties

In speaking, people may find difficulties. As Khan stated in his research that several of his participants have problems to speak. Several factors caused speaking difficulties may come several problems, such as:

1. Linguistic Problem

Linguistic is a study of language, which studies about the language structure (grammar), words and phonology. Generally, linguistic consists of information about vocabulary, pronunciation, and grammar Linguistic problem is the problem that hinders students' speaking skills [3].

According to Richard, several students' problems in speaking are:

a) Vocabulary

Vocabulary is someone's knowledge about words and the meanings. There are two forms of vocabulary and printed vocabulary. Oral vocabulary is the word that we understand when we speak and read it orally .Printed is the word that we understand when we speak and read it silently [6]

Khan (2005) stated that most foreign learners have difficulties to use words and expressions when they speak. This problem occurs because the students do not know how to combine their vocabularies to be a meaningful utterance. b) Grammar

Grammar is the most important part of language. It is a examine, where sentences are established and formatted. Students' problem in grammar is they are not capable of recognizing the regulations of the grammar, so that they cannot speak in English effectively.

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c) Pronunciation

Pronunciation means how to say the words. Students' difficulties in pronouncing word is because they do not know the correct way to spell it. This problem makes the students' pronunciation gone wrong, then the meaning is not appropriate.

2. Psychological Problems

Psychology is a study that study the process of human thought and behavior in interaction with the environment. Psychological problems of speaking are related to students' emotional and physical health that can bring negative impacts to the students' speaking abilities.

3. Less Confident

Self-confidence is someone's capacity in doing good thing with positive thinking. Self-confidence is related to someone's personality, someone's ability, someone's power, that sometimes manifested excessively. Good self-confidence comes from focusing on self.

Less confident may occur because of bad feelings and thinkings, such as feel guilty, shy, unrealistic expectation, false sense of humility, fear, depression, and so on. Less confident can make students become bad speaker. Thus, it is really important to build up students confidents, so that they can express their utterances in good manner when they speak [3].

4. Shyness

Also, shyness is considered main factors that prevents students from speaking because they afraid of doing mistakes and being in a public attention as a result they face difficulties in speaking.

The Strategies in Solving Speaking Problem

These language learning strategies have been differentiated into four main categories and they are described as follows:

a. Cognitive strategies, usually they involve the identification, retention, storage, retrieval of words, phrase, and other elements of the target language (e.g. using prior knowledge to comprehend new language material, applying grammar rule to a new context, or classifying vocabulary according to topic).

b. Meta cognitive strategies, the deal with pre-planning and self-assessment, online planning, monitoring and evaluation, as well as post evaluation of language learning activities. (e.g. previewing the language materials for the day's lesson, organizing one' thoughts before speaking, or reflecting on one's performance).

c. Social strategies include the action that learner select for interacting with other learner, a teacher, or with native speakers (e.g. asking questions for clarification, helping a fellow student complete a task, or cooperating with others).

d. Affective strategies, serve to regulate learner motivation, emotions, and attitude

(e.g. strategies for reducing anxiety, for self-encouragement and for self-reward). (p.4) language learning and use strategies consists of the steps and actions chosen by the learners to take one step further in learning of the foreign language [1].

In conclusion, in order to overcome speaking barriers students should focus on improving their vocabulary, grammar, pronunciation. Also, they should increase their self -confidence and learn to accept their mistakes and should not

afraid of doing errors in speech. Furthermore, using latest technology also helps to overcome speaking barriers

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